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Ultrasonic properties of β -phase nickel aluminide

R.R. YADAV* and D.K. PANDEY

Physics Department, Allahabad University, Allahabad - 211 002

The ultrasonic attenuation due to phonon-phonon interaction has been evaluated in β -phase NiAl in high temperature interval 300-1400K along the crystallographic directions $\langle 100 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ for longitudinal and shear waves. For this evaluation we have calculated second and third order elastic constants (SOEC and TOEC) at the different temperatures using only two basic parameters. Ultrasonic velocities and Non-linearity parameters are calculated using the elastic constants. Structural stability, abrupt change in ductility, disordering at T_C may be predicted on the basis of temperature variation of the elastic constants and the ultrasonic attenuation.

INTRODUCTION

Intermetallic compounds containing aluminium such as NiAl, offer new opportunities for developing low density, high strength structural alloys which might be used at temperatures higher than possible with conventional titanium and nickel-base alloys. Once developed, the intermetallic alloys and their composites will enable the design and production of higher performance, lighter (high thrust-to-weight ratio) engines for future military aircraft and supersonic commercial transport. Strong bonding between aluminium and nickel, which persists at high temperatures, can provide high strength at elevated temperatures such that the specific strength of intermetallics could be competitive with superalloys and ceramics. However, the high strength is usually associated with poor ductility. With respect to ductility, intermetallics fall between metals and ceramics. Intermetallics are not as brittle as ceramics because the bonding in intermetallics is predominantly metallic, compared to ionic or covalent bonding in ceramics. Nickel aluminide (NiAl) has been the

subject of many development programs. The β -phase NiAl (50 at % Ni, 50 at % Al, with a CsCl, B_2 crystal structure) discussed here, is very different from the developed γ' -phase Ni₃Al (75 at % Ni, 25 at % Al, $L1_2$ crystal structure) with respect to physical and mechanical properties. NiAl has four key advantage : its density of $\approx 5.95 \text{ g/cm}^3$ is approximately two thirds the density of state-of-the-art nickel-base superalloys; its thermal conductivity is four to eight times that of nickel-base superalloys (depending on composition and temperature); it has excellent oxidation resistance. NiAl has an ordered body-centered cubic (CsCl) crystal structure, where nickel can be thought of as occupying the corner sites and aluminum the body-centered site. The ordering energy is believed to be very high, which makes dislocation mobility rather difficult. Its simple CsCl structure makes plastic deformation potentially easier compound to many other intermetallic compounds.

One of the potential applications of NiAl is as a high-pressure turbine blade material. Low-density NiAl turbine blades can reduce the turbine rotor weight (blades and disk) by as much as 40%. The thermal conductivity of NiAl is higher than

*E-mail address : rryadav1@rediffmail.com

that of single crystal, nickel-base superalloy. Because of the higher conductivity, the temperature distribution in a NiAl turbine blade is much more uniform and the life-timing "hot spot" temperature is reduced by as much as 50°C¹.

Ultrasonic attenuation spectroscopy is a developed technique for the characterization of the materials not only after production but during the processing as well²⁻⁴. Microstructural phenomena and different mechanical properties are well related to the propagation behaviour of ultrasonic waves for different physical condition of the materials^{5,6}. In the present paper, ultrasonic attenuation, thermal relaxation time, velocity and non-linearity parameters in NiAl are calculated in the temperature range 300-1400K along <100>, <110> and <111> orientations. Elastic properties of the material are required for the evaluation of ultrasonic properties. Therefore we have also calculated the second and third order elastic constants (SOEC and TOEC) of β -Phase NiAl at the different temperatures.

THEORY

For the evaluation of ultrasonic attenuation, second and third order elastic constants (SOEC and TOEC) play an important role. SOEC and TOEC were calculated following Brugger's definition of elastic constants at absolute zero ($C_{\alpha\beta}^0$ and $C_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^0$)^{7,8}. We have established all the formulations for calculation of SOEC and TOEC at different temperatures using the theoretical approach given by Mori, Hiki and P. B. Ghatge^{9,10} for CsCl-type crystals. In the case of CsCl type crystals the potential energy between two ions μ, ν ($=1,2$) with charges $\pm e$ and distance r apart, is assumed to be made up of two parts, coulombic and non-coulombic. Thus

$$\phi_{\mu\nu}(r) = \phi_{\mu\nu}^C(r) + \phi_{\mu\nu}^{NC}(r)$$

where $\phi_{\mu\nu}^C(r) = \pm e^2/r$ and $\phi_{\mu\nu}^{NC}(r) = A \exp(-r/b)$
The expressions for the elastic constants can be easily written down :

$$C_{\alpha\beta}(T) = C_{\alpha\beta}^0 + C_{\alpha\beta}^{Vib}$$

$$C_{\alpha\beta\gamma}(T) = C_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^0 + C_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^{Vib}$$

$$C_{\alpha\beta}^{Vib} = A_{\alpha\beta} \cdot T \quad \text{and} \quad C_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^{Vib} = A_{\alpha\beta\gamma} \cdot T$$

$$\text{where } A_{\alpha\beta} = l_1 k \left. \frac{\partial C_{\alpha\beta}^0}{\partial r} \right|_{r=r_0} + \frac{F_{\alpha\beta}^{Vib}}{TV_C} \quad \text{And}$$

$$A_{\alpha\beta\gamma} = l_1 k \left. \frac{\partial C_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^0}{\partial r} \right|_{r=r_0} + \frac{F_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^{Vib}}{TV_C}$$

Here the elementary cell is taken to have a cube edge of $2r_0$ and volume $4r_0^3 = V_C$. The cell contains one lattice point. The nearest-neighbour distance is $r_1 = r_0\sqrt{3}$. T is temperature in Kelvin.

$$l_1 = -r_0 \left[\left\{ \frac{8}{3} (2\rho_1 + 2\rho_1^2 - \rho_1^3) \phi(r_1) \right\} + \left\{ \frac{3}{2} (2\rho_2 + 2\rho_2^2 - \rho_2^3) \phi(r_2) \right\} \right] Y^{-1}$$

$$Y = \left[\left\{ \frac{8}{3} (\rho_1^2 - 2\rho_1) \phi(r_1) \right\} + \left\{ \frac{3}{2} (\rho_2^2 - 2\rho_2) \phi(r_2) \right\} \right] \left[\left\{ \frac{8}{3} (\rho_1^2 - 2\rho_1) \phi(r_1) \right\} + \left\{ 2(\rho_2^2 - 2\rho_2) \phi(r_2) \right\} \right]$$

where $r_1 = r_0\sqrt{3}$, $r_2 = 2r_0$, $\rho_1 = r_1/b$, $\rho_2 = r_2/b$ and b = hardness parameter and non-coulombic part of energy is assumed to have the form

$$\phi(r) = A \exp(-r/b), \quad \phi(r_1) = A \exp(-r_1/b) \quad \text{and} \\ \phi(r_2) = A \exp(-r_2/b)$$

The constant A is given by

$$A = \frac{bZ_0e^2}{r_0^2} \left[8\sqrt{3} \exp(-\rho_1) + 12 \exp(-\rho_2) \right]^{-1}$$

and $C_{\alpha\beta}^0$ and $C_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^0$ are given as :

$$C_{111}^0 = -\frac{15e^2}{8r_0^4} S_7^{(3)} - \frac{\phi(r_1)}{9b} \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{r_0^2} + \frac{3}{br_0} + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{b^2} \right) \\ - \frac{\phi(r_2)}{2b} \left(\frac{3}{r_0^2} + \frac{6}{br_0} + \frac{4}{b^2} \right)$$

$$C_{112}^0 = C_{166}^0 = -\frac{15e^2}{8r_0^4} S_7^{(2,1)} - \frac{\phi(r_1)}{9b} \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{r_0^2} + \frac{3}{br_0} + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{b^2} \right)$$

$$C_{123}^0 = C_{456}^0 = C_{144}^0 = -\frac{15e^2}{8r_0^4} S_7^{(1,1,1)} \\ - \frac{\phi(r_1)}{9b} \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{r_0^2} + \frac{3}{br_0} + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{b^2} \right)$$

$$C_{11}^0 = \frac{3e^2}{8r_0^4} S_5^{(2)} + \frac{3\phi(r_1)}{br_0} \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3r_0} + \frac{1}{b} \right) + \frac{2\phi(r_2)}{br_0} \left(\frac{1}{2r_0} + \frac{1}{b} \right)$$

$$C_{12}^0 = C_{44}^0 = \frac{3e^2}{8r_0^4} S_5^{(1,1)} + \frac{\phi(r_2)}{br_0} \left(\frac{1}{2r_0} + \frac{1}{b} \right)$$

where lattice sums are :

$$S_1^0 = -Z_0 = -1.017678, \quad S_5^{(2)} = 0.354190, \\ S_5^{(1,1)} = 0.346708, \quad S_7^{(3)} = 0.540901$$

$$S_7^{(2,1)} = -0.093356, \quad S_7^{(1,1,1)} = -0.159996$$

Free energy terms are as :

$$F_{11}^{vib} = \frac{kT}{4} \left(G_2 - \frac{G_1^2}{6} \right), \quad F_{12}^{vib} = \frac{kT}{4} \left(G_{1,1} - \frac{G_1^2}{6} \right),$$

$$F_{44}^{vib} = \frac{kT}{4} G_{1,1}$$

$$F_{111}^{vib} = \frac{kT}{4} \left(G_3 - \frac{1}{2} G_1 G_2 + \frac{G_1^3}{18} \right),$$

$$F_{112}^{vib} = \frac{kT}{4} \left(G_{2,1} - \frac{1}{3} G_{1,1} G_1 - \frac{1}{6} G_2 G_1 + \frac{G_1^3}{18} \right)$$

$$F_{123}^{vib} = \frac{kT}{4} \left(G_{1,1,1} - \frac{1}{2} G_{1,1} G_1 + \frac{G_1^3}{18} \right),$$

$$F_{144}^{vib} = \frac{kT}{4} \left(G_{1,1,1} - \frac{1}{2} G_{1,1} G_1 \right)$$

$$F_{166}^{vib} = \frac{kT}{4} \left(G_{1,1,1} - \frac{1}{2} G_{1,1} G_1 \right), \quad F_{456}^{vib} = \frac{kT}{4} G_{1,1,1}$$

$$G_1 = \left[\frac{8}{9} \phi(r_1) (2\rho_1 + 2\rho_1^2 - \rho_1^3) + \frac{1}{2} \phi(r_2) \right] Z \\ \left[(2\rho_2 + 2\rho_2^2 - \rho_2^3) \right]$$

$$G_2 = \left[\frac{8}{27} \phi(r_1) (-6\rho_1 - 6\rho_1^2 - \rho_1^3 + \rho_1^4) \right] Z \\ \left[+ \frac{1}{2} \phi(r_2) (-6\rho_2 - 6\rho_2^2 - \rho_2^3 + \rho_2^4) \right]$$

$$G_{1,1} = \left[\frac{8}{27} \phi(r_1) (-6\rho_1 - 6\rho_1^2 - \rho_1^3 + \rho_1^4) \right] Z$$

$$G_3 = \left[\frac{8}{81} \phi(r_1) (30\rho_1 + 30\rho_1^2 + 9\rho_1^3 - \rho_1^4 - \rho_1^5) \right] Z \\ \left[+ \frac{1}{2} \phi(r_2) (30\rho_2 + 30\rho_2^2 + 9\rho_2^3 - \rho_2^4 - \rho_2^5) \right]$$

$$G_{2,1} = G_{1,1,1} = \left[\frac{8}{81} \phi(r_1) (30\rho_1 + 30\rho_1^2 + 9\rho_1^3 - \rho_1^4 - \rho_1^5) \right] Z$$

$$Z = \left[\frac{4}{9} \phi(r_1) (\rho_1^2 - 2\rho_1) + \frac{1}{4} \phi(r_2) (\rho_2^2 - \rho_2) \right]^{-1}$$

In the above derivation we have considered the interaction up to second neighbours. We have neglected the Vanderwaal's forces and many body forces.

The second part of our present investigation was to establish a theory for the evaluation of ultrasonic attenuation in NiAl. The Mason and Bateman theory^{11,12} is still widely used to study the behaviour of ultrasonic attenuation at high temperatures ($\approx 300K$) in solids. It is a more reliable theory for studying the anharmonicity of the crystals as it directly involves elastic constants through non-linearity parameters 'D' in the evaluation of the ultrasonic attenuation coefficient (α). We have made use of the phonon-phonon interaction mechanism for the ultrasonic evaluations. The formulations for the calculation of ultrasonic properties at high temperatures can be given as follows.

The thermal relaxation time (t_{th})^{11,12} for a longitudinal wave is twice that of shear waves.

$$\tau_{th} = \tau_{sh} = \frac{1}{2} \tau_{long} = \frac{3K}{C_V (\bar{V})^2} \quad (1)$$

where K is the thermal conductivity, C_V is the specific heat per unit volume and \bar{V} is the Debye average velocity of ultrasonic wave as :

$$\frac{3}{(\bar{V})^3} = \left(\frac{1}{V_l^3} + \frac{2}{V_s^3} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$V_l = \sqrt{\frac{C_{11}}{\rho}} \quad \text{and} \quad V_s = \sqrt{\frac{C_{44}}{\rho}}$$

where V_l and V_s are the velocity of longitudinal and shear wave respectively.

The thermoelastic loss^{11,12} is obtained as :

$$(\alpha/f^2)_{th} = \frac{4\pi^2 \langle \gamma_i^j \rangle^2 KT}{2\rho V_l^5} \quad (3)$$

Where $\langle \gamma_i^j \rangle$ is the average Grüneisen number, j is the direction of propagation and i is the mode of propagation. $\langle \gamma_i^j \rangle$ is related to SOEC and TOEC ¹¹ ρ is the density, T is the temperature in Kelvin and f is the frequency of the wave.

The ultrasonic attenuation coefficient over frequency square $(\alpha/f^2)_{\text{Akh}}$ (Akhieser type loss) due to phonon-phonon interaction mechanism is given by $(\omega\tau \ll 1)$ ¹³

$$(\alpha/f^2)_{\text{Akh}} = \frac{E_0(D/3)4\pi^2\tau}{2\rho V^3} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } D = 9 \langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle - \frac{3 \langle \gamma_i^j \rangle^2 C_V T}{E_0} \quad (5)$$

Here D is the non-linearity parameter for a longitudinal and shear wave and E_0 is the thermal energy density, C_V is the specific heat per unit volume, both are calculated using the physical constant tables and Debye temperature (θ_D).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The computed values of temperature dependent second and third order elastic constants (SOEC and TOEC) of NiAl are presented in Table-1. Ultrasonic velocity for a longitudinal wave (V_L) and that for a shear wave (V_S) are calculated using the values of SOEC. The values of Debye average velocity (\bar{V}) (calculated using the values of V_L and V_S), thermal conductivity (K), thermal energy density (E_0), specific heat per unit volume (C_V) and thermal relaxation time (τ_{th}) are presented in Table 2. Grüneisen numbers and non-linearity parameters (D_L and D_S) for longitudinal and shear waves at different temperatures along $\langle 100 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ directions are calculated using the values of second and third order elastic constants and are presented in Tables 3-5. Finally the temperature variation of ultrasonic attenuation coefficients $(\alpha/f^2)_{\text{Akhlong}}$, $(\alpha/f^2)_{\text{Akhshear}}$ for longitudinal and shear waves respectively and thermo-elastic loss $(\alpha/f^2)_{\text{th}}$ along $\langle 100 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystallographic directions in the range 300-1400K are shown in Figs. 1-3. The order of magnitude of the present values of second and third order elastic constants (SOEC and TOEC) of β -phase NiAl (CsCl B_2 structure) is comparable with that

of cesium halides ¹⁰. The present value of C_{11} is $17.899 \times 10^{10} \text{N/m}^2$ at 300K. The value of C_{11} is $18.56 \times 10^{10} \text{N/m}^2$ in the work of D.Farkas ¹⁴. There is good agreement between the present work and the work of D.Farkas. The present value of C_{44} is $8.833 \times 10^{10} \text{N/m}^2$ at 1400K. The value of C_{44} is $12.3 \times 10^{10} \text{N/m}^2$ in the work of D.Farkas ¹⁴. Therefore the present calculation of C_{11} and C_{44} is justified. The present value of the modulus C_{111} is $-189.69 \times 10^{10} \text{N/m}^2$. The same modulus is $-184.51 \times 10^{10} \text{N/m}^2$ in the work of R. J. Wasilewski ¹⁵. In the present calculation C_{111} is negative. The value of C_{111} for CsCl is negative ¹⁰. Similarly the experimental value of C_{111} for Al is also negative ¹⁶. Therefore our negative value of C_{111} for β -phase NiAl is justified. Thus our calculations of second and third order elastic constants (SOEC and TOEC) are justified. The present formulations for the calculation of higher order elastic constants of NiAl at different temperatures are established.

The ratio $A = 2C_{44}/(C_{11}-C_{12})$ is the measure of elastic anisotropy in the crystal. When we compare the values of SOEC of Ni and Al pure metals at $\approx 300\text{K}$ ^{17,18} with the values of NiAl, we find that the elastic anisotropy of NiAl is lower than the value of Ni and Al. Hence, by proposing that a low value of anisotropy favors instability. We may state that the intermetallic compound NiAl is unstable in comparison to pure metal Ni and Al. However, it is obvious from the Fig. 4 that the anisotropy (A) of NiAl increases with temperature. Thus intermetallic NiAl is stable at very high temperatures (300-1400K).

Perusal of Fig. 1 shows that the ultrasonic attenuation due to thermal relaxation process $(\alpha/f^2)_{\text{th}}$ decreases very fast from 300 to 700K and then it increases gradually from ≈ 800 to 1400K. Similarly Fig.2 shows that the ultrasonic attenuation due to phonon-phonon interaction (Akhieser type loss) for longitudinal wave $(\alpha/f^2)_{\text{Akh.long}}$ decreases from 300 to 700K and then it increases gradually from ≈ 800 to 1400K. Fig.3 shows that the Akhieser type of loss for shear wave $(\alpha/f^2)_{\text{Akh.shear}}$ decreases fast from 300 to 700K and then it remains almost constant.

Behaviour of ultrasonic attenuation at $\approx 700\text{K}$ is very interesting. In all cases the attenuation decreases fast up to this temperature and then it increases gradually from 800K. It is obvious from

Table 1. SOEC and TOEC (10^{10}N/m^2) of NiAl at 300K to 1400K.

SOEC & TOEC → T.[K] ↓	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{44}	C_{111}	C_{112}	C_{123}	C_{144}	C_{166}	C_{456}
300	17.899	1.6276	2.682	-189.69	-95.070	-79.592	-57.978	-63.026	-77.669
350	18.066	1.6268	2.962	-185.93	-95.412	-78.477	-53.261	-58.027	-76.234
400	18.233	1.6259	3.241	-182.17	-95.753	-77.363	-48.544	-53.028	-74.799
450	18.399	1.6251	3.521	-178.41	-96.095	-76.248	-43.854	-48.029	-73.364
500	18.566	1.6243	3.801	-174.66	-96.437	-75.134	-39.111	-43.030	-71.929
600	18.899	1.6227	4.359	-167.14	-97.120	-72.905	-29.677	-33.031	-69.059
700	19.232	1.6211	4.919	-159.62	-97.804	-70.676	-20.243	-23.034	-66.189
800	19.565	1.6195	5.478	-152.09	-98.487	-68.447	-10.809	-13.036	-63.319
900	19.898	1.6179	6.037	-144.58	-99.171	-66.218	-1.376	-3.038	-60.449
1000	20.231	1.6162	6.597	-137.06	-99.854	-63.989	8.057	6.960	-57.580
1100	20.565	1.6146	7.156	-129.54	-100.54	-61.759	17.491	16.958	-54.710
1200	20.898	1.6130	7.715	-122.02	-101.22	-59.531	26.924	26.956	-51.840
1300	21.231	1.6114	8.274	-114.51	-101.90	-57.302	36.358	36.954	-48.970
1400	21.564	1.6098	8.833	-106.99	-102.59	-55.073	45.791	46.952	-46.101

Table 2. Density (ρ), specific heat (C_v), energy density (E_0), Debye average velocity (\bar{v}), thermal conductivity (K), thermal relaxation time (τ_{th}) of NiAl at 300K to 1400K

Parameters → T[K] ↓	ρ (10^3Kg/m^3)	C_v ($10^6\text{Joule/m}^3\text{ }^0\text{K}$)	E_0 (10^8Joule/m^3)	\bar{v} (10^3m/sec)	K ($\text{w/cm.}^0\text{K}$)	τ_{th} (10^{-11}sec)
300	5.950	3.196	6.150	2.378	76.0	126.182
350	5.945	3.269	7.763	2.496	77.0	113.411
400	5.939	3.301	9.392	2.609	78.0	104.148
450	5.934	3.327	11.049	2.716	79.0	96.545
500	5.928	3.352	12.715	2.819	77.0	86.693
600	5.917	3.381	16.044	3.014	77.5	75.717
700	5.906	3.392	19.599	3.194	76.0	65.866
800	5.894	3.397	22.801	3.365	75.5	58.898
900	5.882	3.402	26.107	3.525	76.0	53.928
1000	5.875	3.404	29.544	3.676	74.5	48.583
1100	5.864	3.403	32.817	3.821	72.5	43.772
1200	5.852	3.402	36.140	3.960	73.0	41.045
1300	5.844	3.397	39.560	4.092	70.5	37.177
1400	5.835	3.392	42.874	4.219	67.0	33.279

the Table 3-5 that the Grüneisen parameters $\langle(\gamma_i^j)^2\rangle$, non-linearity constants D_L and D_S contribute to the temperature variation of ultrasonic attenuation. Thermal conductivity (K) and thermal relaxation time (τ_{th}) do not affect to the temperature variation of the total ultrasonic attenuation. The Grüneisen numbers $\langle(\gamma_i^j)^2\rangle$, non-linearity constants (D_L and D_S) are directly calculated using the elastic constants. Thus the

elastic properties of the material affect the temperature variation of the total attenuation.

In both the polycrystalline and single crystal forms, NiAl is brittle at room temperature in most cases and ductile at high temperatures. It is interesting to note that the ductile to brittle transition temperature (DBTT) is only 625 to 700K in different single crystals ¹. There is an abrupt increase in ductility in NiAl over a small range of

Table 3. Average Gruneisen number $\langle \gamma_i^j \rangle_L$ for longitudinal wave, average square Gruneisen number $\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_L$ and $\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_S$ for longitudinal and shear wave, non-linearity parameters D_L , D_S for longitudinal and shear wave of NiAl along [100] direction from 300K to 1400K.

T[K] ↓	$\langle \gamma_i^j \rangle_L$	$\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_L$	$\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_S$	D_L	D_S
300	2.352	26.609	14.615	213.618	131.534
350	2.018	18.802	11.550	151.209	103.950
400	1.736	13.392	9.226	107.821	83.039
450	1.439	9.581	7.430	77.163	66.872
500	1.282	6.867	6.021	55.299	54.188
600	0.931	3.534	4.008	28.527	36.079
700	0.648	1.867	2.712	15.248	24.406
800	0.414	1.111	1.872	9.387	16.847
900	0.217	0.888	1.338	7.825	12.040
1000	0.048	0.979	1.016	8.795	9.140
1100	-0.100	1.257	0.844	11.276	7.594
1200	-0.230	1.648	0.780	14.654	7.025
1300	-0.346	2.106	0.797	18.554	7.172
1400	-0.449	2.601	0.872	22.734	7.847

Table 4. Average Gruneisen number $\langle \gamma_i^j \rangle_L$ for longitudinal wave, average square Gruneisen number $\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_L$ and $\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_S$ for longitudinal and shear wave, non-linearity parameters D_L , D_S for longitudinal and shear wave of NiAl along [110] direction from 300K to 1400K.

T[K] ↓	$\langle \gamma_i^j \rangle_L$	$\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_L$	$\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_S$	$\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_{S^{**}}$	D_L	D_S^*	D_S^{**}
300	-3.044	32.450	7.439	0.565	248.72	66.95	5.09
350	-2.635	23.657	6.123	0.458	182.20	55.10	4.12
400	-2.287	17.473	5.022	0.379	135.19	45.19	3.42
450	-1.985	13.044	4.103	0.323	101.37	36.92	2.91
500	-1.720	9.831	3.337	0.282	76.78	30.03	2.54
600	-1.274	5.762	2.175	0.233	45.70	19.58	2.09
700	-0.909	3.597	1.394	0.214	29.37	12.55	1.93
800	-0.605	2.517	0.892	0.217	21.34	8.03	1.95
900	-0.345	2.083	0.598	0.234	18.33	5.38	2.11
1000	-0.119	2.047	0.459	0.264	18.38	4.13	2.37
1100	0.079	2.263	0.437	0.303	20.34	3.93	2.72
1200	0.256	2.638	0.504	0.349	23.52	4.53	3.14
1300	0.415	3.115	0.639	0.403	27.46	5.75	3.62
1400	0.558	3.656	0.825	0.462	31.87	7.42	4.16

*means shear wave polarized along [001] direction.

**means shear wave polarized along $[1\bar{1}0]$ direction

temperature near the DBTT. Large plastic elongations (>20%) are obtained just above this temperature. Here the ultrasonic attenuation mostly decreases very fast up to around DBTT ($\approx 700K$). Thus the temperature variation of the ultrasonic attenuation seems to predict the abrupt change of ductility nearly at the DBTT. Yield

strength of β -phase NiAl decreases from 800K ¹. This is predicted as the ultrasonic attenuation increases gradually from this temperature in nearly all cases.

The reasons for such abrupt change in ductility are not fully understood. Proposed

Table 5. Average Gruneisen number $\langle \gamma_i^j \rangle_L$ for longitudinal wave, average square Gruneisen number $\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_L$ and $\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_S$ for longitudinal and shear wave, non-linearity parameters D_L , D_S for longitudinal and shear wave of NiAl along [111] direction from 300K to 1400K.

T[K] ↓	$\langle \gamma_i^j \rangle_L$	$\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_L$	$\langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle_S$	D_L	D_S
300	-1.996	25.891	4.263	214.38	38.37
350	-1.751	20.108	3.387	167.42	30.48
400	-1.536	15.748	2.718	131.78	24.46
450	-1.345	12.401	2.198	104.25	19.78
500	-1.174	9.798	1.790	82.73	16.11
600	-0.877	6.149	1.209	52.42	10.89
700	-0.627	3.884	0.844	33.53	7.59
800	-0.411	2.505	0.618	21.94	5.56
900	-0.223	1.721	0.489	15.32	4.39
1000	-0.056	1.347	0.428	12.11	3.85
1100	-0.092	1.263	0.416	11.34	3.75
1200	0.227	1.387	0.442	12.31	3.98
1300	0.348	1.660	0.495	14.54	4.46
1400	0.459	2.043	0.569	17.68	5.12

Fig. 1. $(\alpha/f^2)_{Th}$ vs temperature

Fig. 2. $(\alpha/f^2)_{Akhlong}$ vs temperature

Fig. 3. $(\alpha/f^2)_{AkhShear}$ vs temperature

Fig. 4. Anisotropy vs temp for NiAl

*means shear wave polarized along [001] direction
 ** means shear wave polarized along $[1\bar{1}0]$ direction
 *** means shear wave polarized along $[1\bar{1}0]$ direction

explanation of this behaviour includes the onset of dislocation climb, thermally activated slip, unlocking of dislocations from the interstitial impurities and additional slip systems. It is also interesting to note that a reduction in the degree of ordering in NiAl has been proposed around this temperature (DBTT) ¹⁹, which has been also predicted as the ultrasonic attenuation gradually increases from 800K.

In this way the structural stability, abrupt change in ductility at \approx DBTT, disordering at \approx DBTT could be predicted on the basis of temperature variation of the elastic constants of NiAl and the ultrasonic attenuation in the material from 300 to 1400K.

Our theoretical approach, which was originally formulated for pure metallic crystals, seems to be valid for the characterization of β -phase NiAl intermetallic compound at high temperatures.

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